

Project Acronym	SPARC
Project Title	Support of Personalized medicine Approaches in Cancer
Project Number	101232874

Deliverable Information:

Work Package	WP9
Deliverable related number	D9.5
Deliverable number	D31
Deliverable name	Project website
Deliverable description	SPARC project website aligned and integrated with PCM JA
Lead beneficiary	2 - EAPM
Type	DEC - Websites, patent filings, videos, etc
Related tasks	T9.4: Targeted Communication and Dissemination
Dissemination level	PU - Public
Version	v1.0
Due date	31/01/2026
Delivery date	29/01/2026

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's EU4Health programme under Grant Agreement No **101232874** (SPARC).

Disclaimer

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Revision History:

Version	Date	Comments	Partner
0.1	15/12/2025	Initial table of content	EAPM
0.4	22/12/2025	Initial description of project website	EAPM
0.9	20/1/2026	Content finalized	EAPM,
1	28/1/2026	Document completed and reviewed	EAPM, UPM

Authors:

Name	Partner
Chiara de Tomasso	EAPM
Denis Horgan	EAPM
Sofia Pazzagli	EAPM
Anđela Skarpa	EAPM

Reviewers:

Name	Partner
Silvia Uribe	UPM
Manuel Ottaviano	UPM

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	3
1. Project Visual Identity	3
2. SPARC Website	5
2.1 Website Development Process and Governance	5
2.2 Launch and Initial Implementation	5
2.3 Website Overview and Content Structure	6
3. Synergy with the Joint Action on Personalised Cancer Medicine (JA PCM).....	8
4. Social Media Presence	9
5. Conclusions and next steps	11

List of figures

Figure 1: SPARC logo, with color variation	4
Figure 2: SPARC banner	4
Figure 3: Screenshot of the website homepage.....	6
Figure 4: Screenshot of the “Policy Impact” section.....	7
Figure 5: Screenshot of the “Results” section	8
Figure 6: Newsroom section, with the first issue of SPARC newsletter	8
Figure 7: Screenshot of SPARC X account	10
Figure 8: Screenshot of SPARC LinkedIn page.....	10
Figure 9: Screenshot of SPARC’s LinkedIn first post.....	11

Executive Summary

This deliverable (D9.5) provides an evidence-based overview of the communication, dissemination, and visibility activities implemented by the European Alliance for Personalised Medicine (EAPM) during the early phase of the SPARC project, covering the period from November 2025 to January 2026. It documents the initial steps taken to establish a coherent and recognisable communication framework for SPARC, ensuring a strong foundation for effective outreach, transparency, and stakeholder engagement throughout the project's lifecycle.

The deliverable focuses in particular on the development and launch of the SPARC website, which constitutes the project's central communication and dissemination platform. It describes the website's conceptualisation, structure, governance, and initial implementation, as well as its intended role as a dynamic and evolving hub that will progressively reflect project activities, outputs, and results. In addition, the document outlines the processes underpinning website development, including content planning, internal review, coordination with the project coordinator, and collaboration with external web developers.

Beyond the website, the deliverable also describes the creation of SPARC's visual identity, including the development of the project logo and associated branding materials, as well as the establishment of the project's social media presence across key platforms.

By documenting these activities, this deliverable provides a transparent account of how communication tools and channels have been set up at project start and establishes a reference point for future reporting on dissemination, outreach, and policy engagement activities under WP9.

1. Project Visual Identity

The first communication activity implemented under WP9 was the development of a clear and recognisable visual identity for SPARC. EAPM delivered the final SPARC logo, designed to visually reflect the project's focus on personalised cancer medicine, innovation, collaboration, and patient-centred care. In addition to the logo, EAPM developed a comprehensive branding package, which includes PowerPoint presentation templates and official banners. These assets support harmonised communication across all Work Packages and partners.

Figure 1: SPARC logo, with color variation

Figure 2: SPARC banner

2. SPARC Website

2.1 Website Development Process and Governance

The development of the SPARC website (<http://sparc-project.eu/>) followed a structured process led by EAPM in close alignment with the project coordinator. Initial work focused on defining the overall objectives, key messages, and structure of the website, supported by internal EAPM review rounds to ensure consistency with the project's communication strategy and EU4Health requirements. This process was complemented by regular coordination calls with the external web development team. In parallel, dedicated meetings were held with the project coordinator to align on content priorities, messaging, and the overall narrative of the website.

To support a clear and coherent website structure, EAPM first developed a detailed content and structural framework outlining the main sections of the website, the hierarchy of pages and sub-pages, and the type of information to be presented under each area. Building on this framework, EAPM then prepared a comprehensive content development document in the form of a structured Excel file. This document mapped all website pages and sub-tabs and included the full draft content for each section, serving as the central reference for website development.

The Excel document underwent internal review within EAPM to ensure clarity, coherence, and alignment with the project's communication objectives. It was subsequently shared with the project coordinator for validation and further input. Following approval, the document was provided to the external web development team and used as the basis for the progressive implementation of the website, ensuring an efficient translation of agreed content into the final online structure.

2.2 Launch and Initial Implementation

The website was launched shortly before the project kick-off meeting (Madrid, November 20-21, 2025) ensuring that a complete and consistent online presence was in place from the start of the project. Following launch, the website is managed by EAPM and has been conceived as a dynamic platform that will be updated on a regular basis throughout the project's lifetime. Updates will reflect project progress, milestones, events, and outputs, and will include additional content such as newsletters, deliverables, publications, pilot results, training materials, and policy-related outputs as they become available.

Access for content updates is centrally managed to ensure quality control, consistency of messaging, and alignment with the project's dissemination strategy, while coordination with the project coordinator and relevant Work Package leaders will

ensure that information published on the website remains accurate and timely, so that the website remains a living resource rather than a static repository.

Already following the kick-off meeting, the website has been updated with the first project communication materials, including the inaugural issue of the SPARC newsletter and an official press release.

2.3 Website Overview and Content Structure

The website was conceived as a structured and accessible digital space, designed to present the project in a clear and coherent manner and to support transparency, visibility, and stakeholder engagement throughout the project's duration. Its overall structure reflects the need to communicate complex scientific, clinical, and policy-related content in an intuitive and user-friendly way, with the homepage designed as a long, structured landing page bringing together all essential project information in a single flow.

Figure 3: Screenshot of the website homepage

At this early stage of implementation, the website primarily hosts general and introductory information about the project, including its objectives, scope, thematic focus, and organisational framework. However, it has been explicitly conceived as a dynamic platform, intended to evolve in parallel with the project's activities.

The primary purpose of the website is to provide a clear and comprehensive overview of SPARC, its thematic areas, and its contribution to advancing personalised cancer medicine in Europe. To this end, the website includes dedicated sections addressing all major dimensions of the project. Key sections include:

- **Policy and Impact:** this section presents SPARC’s contribution to EU and national policy objectives, including its alignment with Europe’s Beating Cancer Plan, the EU Health Data Space, and the synergy with the Joint Action on Personalised Medicine (JA PCM).
- **Results:** a dedicated page which will progressively showcase project outputs, including deliverables, publications, and insights generated through the clinical pilots.
- **Cancer Pilots:** it presents the project’s seven clinical pilots across major and rare cancers, illustrating how personalised medicine approaches are being tested and implemented in real-world settings.
- **News:** a dedicated newsroom containing project updates, announcements, newsletters, and highlights from events and workshops.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the “Policy Impact” section

Figure 5: Screenshot of the “Results” section

Figure 6: Newsroom section, with the first issue of SPARC newsletter

3. Synergy with the Joint Action on Personalised Cancer Medicine (JA PCM)

Synergies with other EU initiatives are a core component of SPARC’s communication and dissemination strategy, with particular emphasis placed on the Joint Action on Personalised Cancer Medicine (JA PCM), which represents the project’s primary and mandatory synergy under the EU4Health framework. This collaboration is reflected directly within SPARC’s online communication tools, notably through the project website.

The SPARC website includes a dedicated “Synergies” section, designed to highlight collaboration with related European initiatives. Within this section, specific relevance is given to JA PCM, presenting the rationale for the synergy, areas of alignment, and shared objectives.

Following the official launch of JA PCM, marked by its Kick-Off Meeting in Brussels in January, the SPARC website will be progressively updated to expand this section beyond introductory information. Planned updates will include the integration of additional content jointly produced by SPARC and JA PCM, reflecting the operationalisation of the synergy and its concrete outputs.

A key upcoming update concerns the publication of approximately 40 video interviews recorded during the JA PCM Kick-Off Meeting and currently being edited. These

interviews were conducted collaboratively by SPARC and JA PCM and represent the first tangible communication output arising from the synergy between the two initiatives. The interviews will be hosted on the SPARC YouTube account and website and will contribute to amplifying project messages, sharing stakeholder perspectives, and illustrating alignment between the two initiatives.

In addition, the website will host a dedicated section related to the Stakeholder Coordination Group, a joint activity developed in collaboration between JA PCM (WP2) and SPARC (WP9). This section will support visibility and coordination of stakeholder engagement activities and serve as a reference point for joint efforts aimed at fostering inclusive and structured participation across policy, clinical, research, and patient communities.

Looking ahead, the website will continue to be used as a platform to communicate future developments related to the SPARC–JA PCM synergy. Planned activities include, among others, the publication of a joint annual newsletter, agreed by both initiatives, which will be promoted and made available through the website. Through these ongoing updates, the SPARC website will play a central role in supporting sustained communication, alignment, and knowledge exchange between the two projects over their respective lifecycles.

4. Social Media Presence

SPARC has established an active presence across three social media platforms, all managed by EAPM:

- **LinkedIn** (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/sparc-eu/>)
- **X** (https://x.com/sparc_eu?s=21)
- **YouTube** (https://youtube.com/@sparc-eu?si=VqKz0e7PZ7yN8_uC)

The LinkedIn account, launched in the first half of November 2025, serves as the main platform for sharing project updates, events, milestones, and synergies with other EU initiatives. All LinkedIn posts are systematically mirrored on X to ensure message consistency and broader reach. The YouTube channel hosts audiovisual content, including 20 video interviews recorded during the SPARC Kick-Off Meeting in Madrid, featuring consortium partners and project leaders. Additional video content will be created and published as the project progresses.

Figure 7: Screenshot of SPARC X account

Post della pagina

Figure 8: Screenshot of SPARC LinkedIn page

Figure 9: Screenshot of SPARC's LinkedIn first post

5. Conclusions and next steps

The project website will remain the central entry point for information on SPARC activities and progress, with periodic updates reflecting key milestones and outcomes. In line with Open Science principles, public deliverables and selected project outputs will be made openly available through the SPARC community on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/sparc-project/>), ensuring transparent, long-term access to project results and supporting their reuse beyond the project's lifetime.